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Estuary Shoreline Dynamics: local consequences and adaptation strategies

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ABSTRACT

Estuaries are important ecosystems with an array of diverse species of fauna and flora. These resources and the opportunities they provide make them attractive for human settlement. However, natural and anthropogenic processes have caused the estuarine shoreline to continually undergo changes such as shoreline erosion, transgression and accretion. These changes significant impact on the environment and people. This study examined the impact of estuarine shoreline changes on people and the adaptive responses toward these impacts with the aid of questionnaires, in-depth interviews and observation. The study revealed that estuarine shoreline changes have severely affected the livelihood of 47.5% of the people, severely affected the cost of living of 30% and have temporarily or permanently displaced 86% of the people. Their adaptive strategies include piling with mud and logs, piling with granite stones, building seawalls, and relocating development away from the shoreline. It was recommended that an intervention is necessary to further develop and upscale their piling strategy to protect the shoreline.

Keywords: Adaptive strategies, Estuarine, Shoreline changes, Shoreline protection, Transgression.

INTRODUCTION

Estuarine shorelines serve as critical boundaries between brackish water and freshwater areas, offering a range of ecosystem services (Manning, 2025; MdLusky & Elliot, 2004). These shorelines are typically found along the coast in brackish environments such as sounds, marshes, rivers, and creeks. Major estuaries along Nigeria's eastern coast include the Bonny and Cross River estuaries, which feature both profound and superficial waterways with semi-diurnal tides that produce tidal flows in alignment with tidal movements (Folorunsho & Awosika, 2014).

Estuarine shorelines are crucial for protecting coastal communities and offering ecological benefits by shielding against storms and flooding (McLusky & Elliott, 2004). They are harbours for nutrients and make great nurseries for numerous fish and shellfish species (Manning, 2025). But estuaries are fleeting, and their shorelines experience substantial changes attributable to natural processes such as waves, winds, tidal currents, rainfall, and storms, as well as anthropogenic influences like alterations in land use, urbanisation, building of dams, irrigation water extraction, dredging, and sand or gravel removal (Geoscience Australia, 2025; Danladi et al., 2017).

As sea levels continue to rise due to climate change and other natural and anthropogenic processes undercut estuaries' shorelines, there is an upward and landward relocation of the shoreline (Iliya et al., 2017; Riggs, 2008). These processes are known as transgression and shoreline erosion, respectively. Transgression is the change in shoreline primarily from the rise in sea level (Yincan, 2017), while erosion occurs when the sediments transported out from the shoreline are not replaced equally during deposition on the shoreline (Geoscience Australia, 2025). Both processes result in land loss, a major factor in shoreline change, that damages infrastructure, affects agricultural lands, disrupts habitats for flora and fauna, and alters natural shorelines (Rahman & Rahman, 2015). The many settlements that

grew around coastal areas due to their social and economic benefits have become vulnerable to the impact of these challenges, as they significantly impact the social, economic and physical environments (Maulud et al., 2022; Handayani et al., 2020).

Azhar et al. (2018) investigated the impact of shoreline changes on coastal development in Malaysia using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to create geospatial visualisations and assess changes from Sabak Bernam to Kuala Selangor. Their findings highlighted significant erosion affecting residential areas, schools, and agricultural activities between Sungai Burung and Sungai Panchang Bedena. Otoo et al (2023) researched the shoreline change analysis on the Coastline of Teshie in Accra, Ghana and discovered that the shoreline was attacked by coastal processes and anthropogenic activities that led to changes in morphology and threatened lives and properties. The analysis of the shoreline was conducted using three Landsat images of 1986, 2003 and 2016. The shoreline was analysed using ARCGIS. The results indicated that 40.7% of the total coastline was undergoing erosion, while 59.3% experienced accretion between 1986 and 2016. The average net shoreline movement (NSM) showed an accretion of 12.7 m, with an annual rate of 0.9 m/year. In contrast, the average coastline erosion measured 10.4 m, with an annual erosion rate of 0.7 m/year.

Thus, in some cases, researchers identify accretion as a major shoreline change (Maulud et al., 2022). Shoreline accretion in land area or landscape along the marine edge can pose environmental threats to navigation routes and groundwater discharge to the sea (Wang et al, 2023). These changes arise from shifts in the forces that influence shoreline sediments, such as wind, waves, and currents, through a process known as deposition. Accretion involves the buildup of coastal sediment on the visible portion of a beach or foreshore, often following submersion during rough weather and subsequent deposition during calmer conditions. This process increases the size of materials like rocks and stones on the beach. Bunnett & Okunrotifa (2013) opined that sections of Nigeria's coastline are experiencing rapid erosion, while other areas are undergoing active accretion. These shoreline changes due to erosion and deposition impact communities that depend on the shoreline for their livelihoods, affect agricultural activities, damage infrastructure, alter shoreline geomorphology, and disrupt local flora and fauna (Otoo et al. 2023).

Adaptation strategies for shoreline changes involve proactive measures designed to address and manage the impacts of shoreline alterations. These strategies aim to reduce vulnerability and improve resilience in response to evolving coastal conditions. Ojile et al. (2017) conducted a comparative analysis of vulnerability and adaptation strategies in coastal communities in Nigeria and Senegal and found similarities and differences in their adaptation approaches. The study revealed that while the vulnerabilities faced by these coastal communities are largely comparable, the adaptation strategies employed differ, influenced by varying cultures, environments, socioeconomic conditions, and capacities to respond to observed climate change impacts. Coastal communities in Nigeria stack sandbags along the shore as a protective barrier and build shelters on stilts. The other measures discovered involved structural interventions such as the construction of riverbank embankment, canals and channels. While measures employed in Senegal involved the stacking of sandbags, reinforced nets along the shore, immersing logs or tires partially in the soil along the shore, alongside sandbags for extra reinforcement. Building household shelters with cement blocks, piling empty seashells along the soil, and mangrove reforestation. Their structural measure includes the construction of breakwater, dykes, and walls.

Fabiyi and Yesuf (2016) investigated the dynamics and characteristics of coastal flooding in Nigeria, focusing on implications for local community management strategies. The study explored the impacts of coastal flooding on coastal settlements and identified adaptation strategies employed by these communities. Some of the adaptive measures include the provision of social capital through mutual support, gifts, loans, temporary accommodation and so on from family, friends, and various organisations to cushion the impact. Raft and pile foundations and raised platforms are used to better withstand the pressure from the coastal floods. The creation of alternative pathways for floodwater and the construction of wooden bridges, mud and concrete embankments, culverts and gutters are some of the measures adopted in the coastal areas.

Several adaptation strategies have been developed to mitigate shoreline change impacts. They include beach nourishment, living shore, Seawalls and Revetments, Managed Retreat, Dune Restoration, and Policy and planning. The beach nourishment technique is a strategy that involves adding sand and other sediments to eroded beaches to restore or increase their width and volume. It helps protect

coastal infrastructure, supports tourism, and provides habitat for wildlife (Climate Adapt, 2023; Institute for Water Resources, n.d.). The Living Shores approach uses natural materials like plants, sand, and rocks to stabilise and protect the shoreline (Ayers, 2023). It enhances water quality, offers habitat for marine life, and provides a buffer against erosion and flooding.

Seawalls and Revetments are hard structures constructed along the shoreline to guard against wave action and erosion. While they effectively reduce erosion, they can also negatively impact adjacent shorelines and ecosystems (National Park Service, 2019). Managed Retreat strategy involves relocating coastal development away from areas vulnerable to erosion and flooding, allowing natural migration of coastal ecosystems and minimising risks to human lives and property (O'Donnell, 2022). Dunes serve as natural barriers against wave action and erosion. Restoring dunes by planting vegetation and installing fencing can stabilise the shoreline and protect inland areas from storm surges and erosion (Superior Groundcover Incorporated, 2021). Effective land-use planning and zoning regulations that account for the dynamic nature of coastlines can support sustainable coastal management practices. By integrating these strategies and tailoring them to the specific characteristics of each coastal area, communities can better manage shoreline changes and enhance resilience to coastal hazards (Pace, 2013).

This research seeks to highlight the consequences of estuarine shoreline change on the livelihood and well-being of the people in communities in the study area and identify the adaptive strategies of the people to the impact of estuarine shoreline change on the communities in the study area.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilised a survey research design. Data for this study were collected from the Twon-Brass and Egwe-Ama communities, 2 communities bordering the Brass River estuary on the east and the west of its shoreline, respectively, in Brass Local Government Area, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Data were gathered through the administration of questionnaires, in-depth interviews, and observations. The population of Twon-Brass was 8,025 in 1991 and was projected to be 40,789 in 2024. For Egwe-Ama, the population was 8,102 in 1991 and was projected to reach 22,918 by 2024. The 1991 census figures were used for the projection because no other official figures have been released for localities in Nigeria other than the 1991 census figures. Using Taro Yamane's formula, a sample size of 400 was determined. 400 copies of questionnaires will be administered in the study area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact of shoreline changes on the Population

Table 1: Impact of shoreline changes on the reduction of the Community size

Land loss	Twon-Brass	Egwe-Ama	Total
Yes	226 (88.3)	102 (70.8)	328 (82.0)
No	30 (11.7)	42 (29.2)	72 (18.0)
Total	256(100.0)	144(100.0)	400 (100.0)

Source: Authors' Field Work

Table 1 shows that 82.0% of the respondents from both communities agree that shoreline changes have reduced the size of their communities, and 72 (18%) respondents from both communities don't agree that estuarine shoreline change reduced the size of their communities.

Table 2: Effect on Cost of Living

Level of Effect on Cost of Living	Twon-Brass	Egwe-Ama	Total
Slight	121 (47.3)	79 (54.9)	200 (50.0)
Moderate	51 (19.9)	29 (20.1)	80 (20.0)
Severe	84 (32.8)	36 (25.0)	120 (30.0)
Total	256 (100.0)	144 (100.0)	400 (100.0)

Source: Authors' Field Work.

Table 2 shows that estuarine shoreline changes have slightly affected the cost of living of 200 (50%) respondents from both communities, 120 (30%) respondents from both communities have been moderately affected, and 80 (20%) respondents from both communities have been severely affected.

Table 3: Impact on Livelihood

Impact of Livelihood	Twon-Brass	Egwe-Ama	Total
Slightly	55 (21.5)	15 (10.4)	70 (17.5)
Moderate	96 (37.5)	44 (30.6)	140 (35.0)
Severe	105 (41.0)	85 (59.0)	190 (47.5)
Total	256 (100.0)	144 (100.0)	400 (100.0)

Source: Authors' Field Work.

Table 3 shows that estuarine shoreline change has slightly affected the livelihood of 190 (47%) respondents from both communities, 140 (35%) respondents from both communities said it moderately affected their livelihood, and 70 (18%) said it severely affected their livelihood.

Table 4: Distribution of Displaced Persons

Displacement	Twon-Brass	Egwe-Ama	Total
Yes	218 (85.2)	126 (87.5)	344 (86.0)
No	38 (14.8)	18 (12.5)	56 (14.0)
Total	256 (100.0)	144 (100.0)	400 (100.0)

Source: Authors' Field Work.

Table 4 shows that 56 (14%) respondents from both communities have not been displaced, and 344 (86%) respondents from both communities have been displaced before due to estuarine shoreline change.

Findings from this study show that the livelihood and the well-being of the people of Twon-Brass and Egwe-Ama communities have been affected by estuarine shoreline change. Estuarine shoreline change has slightly affected the cost of living of 200 (50%) respondents from both communities, 120 (30%) respondents from both communities have been moderately affected, and 80 (20%) respondents from both communities have been severely affected.

Estuarine shoreline changes have severely affected the livelihood of 47.5% of the respondents, moderately affected 35% and slightly affected 17.5% of the respondents. Livelihoods like fishing and trading have been severely affected. 56 (14%) respondents have not been displaced, and 344 (86%) respondents have been displaced either temporarily or permanently from their residences or businesses due to estuarine shoreline change and associated inundation. Most fishermen/ women have their stalls on the estuarine shoreline, to be more easily accessible to fishing boats and vessels that ply the Atlantic Ocean. Due to estuarine shoreline change, their shops and docks have been washed away, and they are forced to relocate inland. The cost of setting up new infrastructure is now expensive; therefore, the cost of living has proportionally increased. Also, the cost of setting up new docks for their boats, since the old ones have been washed away due to estuarine shoreline change, is now expensive. So, the price of every kill has been increased. This is in line with assertions of Handayani et al. (2020), who opine that shoreline erosion in coastal areas has reduced income and livelihood opportunities. According to Barua et al. (2024), displaced people witness their residences and businesses being washed away by the persistent shoreline coastal erosion and require intervention from relevant stakeholders to manage these issues.

Figure 1: Showing how erosion has washed away a road and the vulnerable position of a historical relic, the UAC headquarters during the colonial period in Twon-Brass

Source: Authors' Field Work

Adaptive Measures to Estuarine Shoreline Changes

Table 5: Ideal Preventive Measures of Estuarine Shoreline Erosion in the study area

Preventive Measures	Twon-Brass	Egwe-Ama	Total
Piling with Mud and logs	166 (64.8)	83 (57.6)	249(62.3)
Piling with Granite Stones	35 (13.7)	25 (17.4)	60 (15.0)
Building of Seawall	15 (5.9)	15 (10.4)	30 (7.5)
Dwelling away from the shoreline	40 (15.6)	21(14.6)	61 (15.2)
Total	256 (100.0)	144(100.0)	400 (100.0)

Source: Authors' Field Work

Table 5 shows that 249 (62.3%) respondents opined that piling their environment with mud and logs is the ideal adaptive measure against shoreline erosion in the area. 60 (15.0%) respondents perceive that piling with granite stones is the ideal method. 30 (7.5%) respondents prefer to prevent estuarine shoreline erosion by building Seawalls, while 61 (15.2%) respondents prefer to dwell entirely away from the estuarine shoreline as a preventive measure for estuarine shoreline erosion.

Twon-Brass and Egwe-Ama are fishing communities, they have survived and adapted to their shoreline change for decades. There are a couple of adaptive strategies which they employ. Some of their adaptive strategies are crude and traditional, but they work for them.

Piling With Mud and Logs

Piling is a frontline defence against floods, providing a barrier that helps prevent water intrusion into critical areas. It's like the creation of an artificial coastline. The people of Twon-Brass and Egwe-Ama practice two types of piling methods based on the material used for piling. Most people who live along the shoreline or have structures there employ this means to push back encroaching water, usually from high tides and destructive waves. It is a means of land reclamation. Firstly, long logs or bamboo sticks are secured halfway into the ground in the portion of land to be reclaimed or preserved. Secondly, muddy soil is dug from their mangrove swamp to fill the place or portion they have marked out with the logs/bamboo sticks. They usually fill the place up to 3 feet above the ground at least. The mud solidifies after a couple of days and hardens. The mud usually contains dead plant and animal remains, so it is very fertile and supports the growth of plants. Sometimes, trees are planted to hold the soil together.

Figure 2. Piling with chikoko mud and logs in Egwe-Ama.
Source: Authors' Field Work

Piling With Granite Stones

This is a means of shoreline protection, but it is not used for land reclamation. In this process, big stones of granite are piled along the shore, on the exact portion to be protected, usually, 3 feet above the ground. Then, fibre nets are used to hold the granite stones together, to prevent them from falling into the water. Waves smash on the stones, but it is difficult for the backwash of the waves to take away any particles from the shore. Most people use this method of piling because of its aesthetics; it makes the shore good to look at and more comfortable to be on. Figure 3 is an image of granite stone piling in the study area.

Figure 3. Showing piling with granite stones in Twon-Brass.
Source: Authors' Field Work

Building of Seawall

A seawall is a form of coastal defence constructed where the sea and associated coastal processes impact directly upon the landforms of the coast. The purpose of a seawall is to protect areas of human habitation, conservation, and leisure activities. Seawalls work by reflecting incident wave energy back into the sea, thus reducing the energy available to cause erosion. As a seawall is a static feature, it will conflict with the dynamic nature of the coast and impede the exchange of sediment between the land and the sea. A seawall is a structure made of reinforced concrete, masonry or sheet piles, boulders, steel or gabions. It is built parallel to the shore at the transition between the beach and the mainland or dune, to protect the inland area against wave action and prevent coastal erosion. Seawall design pattern is based on the climate, coastal position, wave regime (determined by wave characteristics and effects) and type of land form (morphological characteristics). There are three types of seawalls: Vertical seawalls, curved seawalls and mounds (Davie, 2020). They use the vertical seawall shown in Figures 4 and 5 in the study area. The seawall in Figure 5 was done to protect the jetty from erosion and is the only government effort toward shoreline mitigation in the study area. One of the shortcomings of this type of seawall is that it can suffer a lot of damage in a short period. Vertical seawalls can be undercut by high wave energy environments after a while.

Figure 4: Showing a private Seawall in Twon-Brass
Source: Author Field Work

Figure 5: Public seawall to protect the jetty in the Twon-Brass

Building Of Dwellings Away from the Shoreline

Most people build their houses and other infrastructures far from the shoreline to avoid erosion. The first church (St Barnabas Anglican Church) that was built by the missionaries and numerous businesses and residences, has been washed away by erosion. Figure 1 shows that the road along the shoreline has eroded, and the United African Company (UAC) building, built during the colonial era, is vulnerable to the impact of shoreline erosion. Many new developers opt to build far from the shoreline and move to the interior part of the town, both in Twon-Brass and Egwe-Ama communities. Jetties and mini-fuel stations are the most common new structures built on the shorelines. The mini-fuel stations are built on the shorelines for easy access for boats to load fuel with the added advantage of proximity to water, in the event of a fire outbreak.

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that estuarine shoreline changes have led to land loss and thus flooding, affecting livelihoods, infrastructure, and residential patterns. It reveals that eroding shorelines are impacting the size and expansion of both communities. 82% of the study population believes shoreline changes have impacted their community size. 17.5% of the study population feel that shoreline changes have slightly affected their livelihoods, 35% report moderate effects, and 47.5% experience severe impacts. Additionally, 86% of the study population have been displaced temporarily or permanently, while 14% of respondents have not been displaced due to shoreline changes and/or flooding.

To address these issues, adaptation strategies have been implemented. They include piling with mud and logs, piling with granite stones, building seawalls, and relocating development away from the shoreline. Considering the hardships caused by the impact of shoreline erosion and the community response to mitigate the problem, we recommend that the relevant stakeholders, such as NGOs and the government, intervene by modifying and upscaling the local piling methods to adapt the living shore method. This is to improve the extent of coverage, durability and aesthetics of the shoreline protection method.

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